

Intersectionality of Language and Mathematics in a Math Intelligent Tutoring System: towards Biliteracy, Diversity, Equity and Inclusion

Ivon Arroyo, Danielle Alessio, Dilean Bermudez, Kyle Lee, Marialuisa DiStefano, and Beverly Woolf

University of Massachusetts-Amherst, Amherst, MA 01003, USA
ivon,allessio,dbermudezbe,kaiyuanlee,marialuisadi,bev @umass.edu

Abstract. We created educational technologies for multilingual learners by enhancing features of an intelligent tutoring system that respects Latinx culture and language. First, we fully localized an intelligent mathematics tutor to a South American country, which addressed motivational aspects of learning to the language and culture of the country. Results yielded a significant improvement in mathematics performance and showed an affective improvement on students' grit. Second, we supported diverse learners in the USA by making learning materials, activities and learning companions comprehensible and culturally appropriate for bilingual students who speak Spanish at home.

Keywords: Intelligent tutoring system · bilingualism · mathematics

1 Introduction

The education technology community is committed to the rational introduction of learning technologies for all people (e.g., [3]). For example, immigrant children arrive in the USA with rich funds of knowledge that are not necessarily valued in their classes. Because of inequitable access to resources, Hispanic students in the USA lag well behind non-Hispanic academically, with 77 % graduation rates from high school [9]. Hispanic students do not have quality language instruction in English-only classroom settings, as they must learn the content and develop curricular skills while also learning a new language. Supporting Hispanic students, and other students who do not speak the main language of the country they reside in, is important for social justice. The community addresses the economic, socio-cultural, political and other constraints that shape the implementation and affordances of learning technologies for everyone.

Hispanics are the largest minority group in the USA, and one of its fastest-growing groups. Creating learning technologies only for English speakers seems a missed opportunity since learning technologies are a key scalable solution to reaching students. For example, only 1.5 billion (20%) people on the planet speak English and 22% of residents in the USA now speak a language other than English at home [17]. Thus increased interest exists to expand the reach of

learning technologies, and to export instructional technology generated in developed countries. Latinx, or Hispanics from Latin America (Mexico, South/Central America) and the Caribbean has quadrupled since the 80s, continues to grow [10] and are highly underrepresented (8% of workers) in science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM) [11]. English learners (EL) generally underperform at school compared to students who are English proficient. In mathematics, the average score for 4th-grade EL students was 26 points lower than that of their English-speaking peers and 40 points lower at the 8th-grade level. Mathematics teachers are underprepared to teach integrated math content. As the number of ELs grows, so does the risk of widening the achievement gap between them and their English-speaking peers.

This article first describes a bilingual study of students in Argentina who used an intelligent tutor, MathSpring, in Spanish and in English and the impact these interactions had on their mathematics and language knowledge/skills and their affective relationship to math and learning. Secondly, this article reports on current efforts to implement a bilingual MathSpring within the USA, so that learning materials, activities and learning companions are comprehensible and culturally appropriate for bilingual Spanish-speaking students. We created equitable educational technologies for Hispanic students by enhancing features of an intelligent tutoring system (ITS) that respects their cultures and language.

Research questions of the work presented here include: RQ#1: What does localization of learning software to a Latino sub-culture entail?; RQ#2: How does the implementation of localized software support mathematics and language learning? RQ#3: Does the intelligent tutor have a positive affective impact given the growth-mindset training in MathSpring? RQ#4: Which character that speaks a different language do Latinx students in the USA choose, when given a choice, and what is their perception of multicultural learning companions?

MathSpring Intelligent Tutoring System The intelligent tutor we use in both bilingual projects is MathSpring.org, a game-like, freely available, multimedia platform used by tens of thousands of students [1], (see Fig 3). Ample evidence exists that MathSpring provides a positive academic and affective impact when used *in English in the USA*. In controlled studies, students showed an increase in mathematics and reading comprehension, (see Fig 2). It is game-like (students grow gardens that visually represent their mathematics progress), intelligent (builds an internal model of students, as would a good teacher), and provides personalized content and remedial tutoring when needed. For instance, MathSpring might be set to teach Grade 7 mathematics and it will seamlessly move back to grade 6 and 5 material as needed, and unnoticeable to the student.

MathSpring is affective, in that animated “learning companions” (LC) provide support for socio-emotional skills (in between math problems) through prompts that ask students how they feel. Students’ academic emotions (e.g., frustration, anxiety, interest) are positively impacted by the LC [1]. The tutor offers support when students become frustrated or anxious, delivering 70 different messages after assessing a student’s emotional state [1]. These affective characters also

train students' "growth mindset" [8], encouraging them to consider mistakes as a natural part of learning and stating that intelligence is malleable.

We know that these pedagogical agents makes a significant positive impact on student learning and behavior, especially when the character matches the self-identified gender of the student (e.g., [2] [4] [5] [7] [12] [13] [14] [15] [16]). MathSpring has traditionally offered a choice of gender for the characters involved, either an English-speaking female, or an English-speaking male.

2 CultivandoMatematica/MathSpring in South America

In one first project that investigated the intersectionality between language, culture and tutoring systems, we localized MathSpring to Argentina and called it *CultivandoMatematica*, a fully Spanish-speaking tutoring system (see Fig. 1). We created Spanish versions of the English problems and a male South American Spanish-speaking LC. Problems were localized to Argentinian math notation and accent. This localization involves transforming imagery, tone, currency, imperial to metric system, numerical notation, and even more to account for cultural and regional nuances; localization does not just involve translation, so that the learning materials and activities are comprehensible and culturally appropriate for the target audience.

Methodology of Localization to Argentina. We enhanced MathSpring's features to support 150 learners who were 6th-grade students from three (3) schools in Cordoba, Argentina. We created a fully localized Spanish version of MathSpring, called "CultivandoMatematica" (cultivating math) that contained math problems localized to Argentine Spanish, and a male South American Spanish-speaking LC, called "Lucas". Problems were localized to Argentinian notation, accent and variations in curricula. The localization of *CultivandoMatematica* involved three independent levels: a) Spanish of the menus by setting the language of the browser; b) language and context of the math problems, that paralleled problems in English, based on the USA Math Common Core Standards, as well as new math problems created to emphasize areas of math that were not considered central to USA schools (e.g. unit conversions within the metric system for liquid, mass and length); c) localization of Spanish speaking affective characters who spoke in Spanish with a local accent.

Students used *CultivandoMatematica* in one math class/week for five weeks, for an estimated total of five(5) hours of use. In addition, one school was dual-language English-Spanish, and used *MathSpring* in English one additional afternoon a week, during the five weeks, for about 5 additional hours.

Students received three tests (before/after using the software) to measure the impact of the tutor on Argentine children: 1) a Spanish 10-question math test created to assess students' math problem-solving ability that covered the same math content as the software; b) an 8-item "grit" test that measured passion and perseverance for long-term goals [6], translated to Spanish; c) a test at the intersection between English and mathematics (only for students who used

e. musumeci - Bernardez-6to B (poblano)
Topic: Addition/Subtraction of Decimals | Standards: 5.NBT.7.as

$0,48 + 0,6 = ?$

Podemos usar el modelo que se muestra aquí para ayudarte a encontrar el resultado.

Cada cajita pequeña tiene un valor de 0,01 mientras que la caja entera tiene un valor de uno. Cada barra vertical tiene un valor de 0,1.

0,486

Submit Answer! ✗

Step 1 Step 2

0,48+0,60

Ahora se puede sumar como cualquier otro número, pero que no se te olvide alinear la coma del decimal.

Estas son las preguntas difíciles que me gustan. Hay una oportunidad de aprender! Hagamos click en el botón de ayuda.

Fig. 1. The ‘Practice Area’ of CultivandoMatematica. Students solve problems with support of the tools to the left, where the “Ayuda” button explains each problem-solving step (read aloud to the student) and other scaffolds (examples, videos). Math problems are either short answer, multiple choice, or check-all-that-apply. Lucas (right) is an affective LC, a pedagogical agent who empathizes with the student and instills the importance of effort and perseverance.

MathSpring in English), where students had to write, in English, what the math questions asked them to do. These last questions were coded for students’ English language ability and NOT for mathematical accuracy/correctness.

Results of Localization to Cordoba, Argentina. We had full mathematics pre- and post-test data for 141 students, for whom a paired samples t-test analysis yielded a significant improvement in mathematics problem-solving performance from day 1 to day 7 (mean pretest score: $M = 0.43$, $SD = 0.21$; mean posttest score: $M = 0.49$, $SD = 0.21$; paired-samples t-test: $t = 2.88$, $df = 140$, $p < 0.005$). The test covered all the areas of mathematics problems in the software. While there was an improvement in the overall test, the largest improvement was in math problems involving Fractions (Cohen’s $d=0.27$, $p<0.002$), where students spent most time, as fractions was the topic that came first in *CultivandoMatematica*, and due to the personalized capabilities, they tended to spend more time in those first topics. This provides evidence in support of *CultivandoMatematica* as a supplement to math classroom instruction in Spanish, with curriculum/software localized to a South American culture.

Secondly, we analyzed for any potential changes in the affective test of grit –perseverance and passion for long-term goals. Full data for one hundred and

forty-four (144) students were available. A paired-samples t-test showed that the mean measurement of grit differed between pretest time ($M = 3.27$, $SD = 0.53$, $N = 144$) and posttest time ($M = 3.44$, $SD = 0.58$, $N = 144$) at a .001 level of significance ($t = 4.06$, $df = 143$, $p < 0.001$). Students saw an increase in grit after seven weeks of using *CultivandoMatematica*. While this was not a controlled study, there was no other affective curriculum in place at the moment, thus, we believe that grit improvement is attributable to the affective digital characters who instilled perseverance, providing growth mindset messages and empathizing with them in their own local Spanish accent.

For the subset of students in the bilingual school, who took the English as a Second Language (ESL) test involving open-ended word problems comprehension questions, we coded pre and post-test answers using a 0-6 scale rubric that scored for: a) quality and development of central idea, b) expression of ideas, and c) awareness of task and mode. After this coding a pre to post-test analysis showed a significant improvement in students' reading and listening comprehension of English language (coders were blind to whether the test they coded was a pretest or a post-test).

Fig. 2. English as a Second Language (ESL) students were asked to explain what an open-ended word problem was asking (in English) and how they would solve it. Pre- to Posttest changes in reading comprehension of math word problems (left) and listening comprehension of spoken math word problems (right) showed improvement in their English Language skills, after using MathSpring in English.

Interestingly, these results suggest that students learned English language as they used MathSpring in English, at least within the context of mathematics word problems. Thus, MathSpring appears to be not only a tool for mathematics learning, and for affective (grit) development, but also a tool to foster literacy development (See Fig. 2).

3 Bilingual MathSpring for Latinx in the USA

In the second bilingual research project, we addressed the reality of teaching mathematics to Latinx students in the USA. We enhanced the intelligent tutor so students can “switch” between languages (Spanish/English) and choose among

learning companions (LC) that better reflect their diversity. This is different from CultivandoMatematica, in that it constitutes a dual-language MathSpring, with choice of language for the next problem requested and students can go back and forth between languages within the same tutoring session, (see Fig 3).

This current research addresses the following research questions: a) How do students perceive bilingual characters? b) Do students value the choice of language for solving math problems? c) Do students improve in their dual language skills (Spanish/English) by using MathSpring? We localized MathSpring

Fig. 3. MathSpring Bilingual Practice Area interface. Students work with English problems by clicking on "Next Problem" or on Spanish problems by clicking "Proximo Problema". Hints are available (with audio) along with worked-out examples, tutorial videos, and formulas. Isabel (right) is Spanish-speaking and suggests the importance of effort and perseverance in the precise moment students make mistakes.

problems to North American Spanish (SPNA) and created new characters with Puerto Rican accents. During April 2023, we completed a pilot study at an afterschool program in a district that is 52% Latinx. The online tutor contained bilingual math problems and students could choose bilingual LCs that spoke in either Spanish or English. Students used MathSpring to practice for the Massachusetts Standardized State Exam in mathematics.

Learning Companion Choice. For this study, we built a North American Spanish-speaking female LC, Isabel, to add to the suite of LC options. In the future, she will speak both languages, so that she closer represents the experience of emergent bilingual students in the USA (i.e., using all their linguistic repertoire, instead of two monolinguals in one person). We completed a study with students in a high Latinx after-school program and queried their experience about choosing from a suite of LCs and the option to work with Jane or Jake (English speaking) or Lucas or Isabel (Spanish speaking)).

Problem-solving Language Choice. Spanish versions of MathSpring’s English problems were created, to support children who speak Spanish at home. For this study, we built Spanish versions of English problems localized to notations and accent. MathSpring.org was altered to show math word problems in English or Spanish, depending on whether students clicked on "Next Problem" or "Proximo Problema", and they engaged with pedagogical hints (depending on the problem language) that stepped them through solutions in either language, (see Fig. 3).

Methodology. This was an exploratory mixed-methods research study; students took a pretest that explored demographic information about gender identity and language (Which gender identity do you most identify with? How good would you say your Spanish is? How good would you say your English is?) (see Fig 4). The post-test survey explored perceptions of language and learning companion choices. Twenty (20) students from a district in which 53% identify as Hispanic/Latino engaged with MathSpring (MS) for three sessions of at least 30 minutes each session. Students were 5th-6th graders, 7 identified as female and 13 identified as males. Students had the option to choose one of four learning companions avatars (English/Spanish) at the beginning of each session (after logging in), and also to choose the next problem language ('Next Problem' or 'Proximo Problema'). As explained next, we gave students a post-tutor survey to analyze whether students valued the choice of language for the math problems and whether it was helpful to pick problems in either language. A quantitative+qualitative survey included closed and open-ended questions. We assessed the perception of the bilingual characters, by asking students the following post-test survey questions: *a) After logging in to MathSpring, what learning companion did you choose most often? Why?; b) Do you relate to the learning companion that you choose most often?; c) Does the learning companion that you choose most often represent you?,* (see Fig. 5).

Results. Students tended to say they are able to speak spanish "a lot", and many of them said they were dominant in Spanish (see Figure 4).

Regarding students’ choice of language of characters, qualitative results revealed that the learning companion choice was made based on the language

Fig. 4. Students’ self-report on gender/primary language. Students’ self-report on their gender/primary language (left) and their Spanish language ability (right).

Fig. 5. Mean of students' responses to questions about their choice of learning companion (left) and choice of math problems' language (right).

students were taught in, saying they preferred to work with an *English* learning companion because they speak English "better". This seems reasonable as students are schooled in English generally, and it contradicts the fact that students speak Spanish quite a bit, both at home and at school (see Fig. 4). Yet, students tended to choose english-speaking characters, while at the same time they were neutral in their feeling that the learning companion represented them, and somewhat lower than neutral about relating to this LC. It is unclear how students' biases might have affected their choices and we are still analyzing data to understand what influenced the choice of learning companion.

4 Discussion and Conclusion

Students chose the characters who spoke in English, but at the same time they say they only "neutrally" represent them. It is very possible that having a character who can start speaking in English but could switch to Spanish occasionally might be better for these students, engendering the feeling that they are both represented and that the learning companion reflects them also.

We have many new research questions for our future research, e.g. we want to explore how student choice of language and character may differ for Latinx students who are part of dual language programs in the USA, compared to students who are Latinx and part of English Learner (EL) classes, compared to Latinx students who have been schooled in English only.

One conclusion of this research is that a huge potential exists for smart learning technologies to address issues of culture, language, address identity factors in STEM education, and the potential to personalize learning for individual needs that go beyond cognitive needs, and to reach students from varied cultural backgrounds and linguistic repertoires, and the importance of *multi-lingualism*.

A concrete plan moving forward is to support students to design their own learning companions in MathSpring and to switch languages more seamlessly.

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